

REAL-TIME NOTATION USING BRAINWAVE CONTROL

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ABSTRACT

We present a significant extension to our work in the field of Brain-Computer Music Interfacing (BCMI) through providing brainwave control over a musical score in real time. This new approach combines measuring Electroencephalogram (EEG) data, elicited via generating Steady State Visual Evoked Potentials (SSVEP), with mappings to allow a user to influence a score presented to a musician in a compositional and/or performance setting.

Mind Trio is a generative BCMI composition based upon a musical game of 18th century origin. It is designed to respond to the subjective decisions of a user allowing them to affect control over elements of notation, ultimately directing parameters that can influence musical dramaturgy and expression via the brain. We present the design of this piece alongside the practicalities of using such a system on low-cost and accessible equipment.

Our work further demonstrates how such an approach can be used by multiple users and musicians, and provides a sound foundation for our upcoming work involving four BCMI subjects and a string quartet.

1. INTRODUCTION

The aim of our research is to develop musical systems with creative applications for users of all physical abilities. Specifically, we are concerned with the control of brain signals and the application of this feature for musical performance and composition.

The idea of applying brainwaves to music is not new. Experimental composers of the 1960's incorporated amplified brain signals measured via EEG into their work after the reported discovery of voluntary alpha wave (electrical signals of approximately 8-12Hz) control by Dr Joe Kimaya [1, 2]. The composer Alvin Lucier applied this method of neurofeedback in his 1965 piece *Music for a Solo Performer*, and David Rosenboom expanded the field of biofeedback and the arts throughout the 1970s [3]. Until recently using alpha and other low frequency rhythms as input to a musical system dominated applications of music performance technologies and composing with brainwaves [4] [5].

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The last decade has brought about strong advances in the fields of Brain-Computer Interfacing (BCI) and brain signal processing techniques to the extent that computer based musical engines can now be directly controlled via harnessing EEG signals in real-time. Brainwave control of musical parameters has already been researched in [6] [7], and the SSVEP technique we present here has previously been used in musical applications for therapeutic and creative purposes [8] [9]. In Sections 4 and 5 of this paper we outline some considerations in our design of a portable BCMI platform, and introduce a proof-of-concept composition using SSVEP to affect a musical score, for presentation to a pianist.

2. BCMI SYSTEMS

BCMI systems vary in regard to the nature of human-computer interactivity. Computers in user-orientated systems attempt to learn the meaning of the input, a users' EEG, in an attempt to adapt to its behaviour. These systems are useful when variable or unpredictable brain information exists; variable either by lack of control, individual user differences in response to stimuli or the type of the input signal being read. For example a time locked Event Related Potential (ERP) such as a P300 response may vary across a range of amplitudes per user [10], or a generative musical system could be designed based on unpredictable activity across a range of frequency bands. Early musical systems with EEG input are regarded as user-orientated systems, such as Richard Teitelbaum's *In Tune* [11] whereby an analogue synthesiser adapts to the incoming alpha via the EEG, albeit via a human operator. Computer-orientated systems require a user to adapt to the functions of the computer; the success of the system relies on the users' ability to learn how to perform the tasks that translate to musical control. Mutually-orientated systems are a combination of the previous two.

If user control of a system's input range is achievable then a computer-orientated approach can be deemed suitable for systems designed with finite control in mind. The system presented here adopts this computer-orientated approach; a user controls the notation through the pre-determined rules of the computer's mappings. In our future work aside from the aforementioned use of user-orientated systems for interpreting non-meaningful data recording, incorporating a mutually-orientated approach to measure other unpredictable, but perhaps mean-

ingful information, such as emotional arousal [12] within EEG may provide further layers of musical expression.

2.1 Musical Applications of BCMI

Musical engines of BCMI systems are designed for either the sonification or musification of EEG data, or for musical control. Some complexity can be added to systems through applying a combination of these approaches, depending on the objective. Sonification, the process of mapping data to sound, is often used in medical BCMI systems, for example to audibly identify deficiencies or abnormalities in brain signals; in a way not too dissimilar to the function of a stethoscope amplifying a heartbeat. This approach has been used in research into treating illnesses such as ADHD [13] and epilepsy [14]. Musification of brainwave information is the process of mapping brain signals to musical parameters and this is often the case when brain signals are largely uncontrollable and random in nature. Musical control systems utilise a user's cognitive ability to affect control over their brain waves. This provides a framework for designing BCMI tools that can respond to the subjective choices of a user, a *mental gesture*, so to speak.

2.2 BCMI Components

Our BCMI system is built using the following elements:

- *EEG Input* – Electrodes placed on the scalp, in the form of a headband.
- *EEG Analysis* - Amplification of electrical activity, and data extraction to isolate meaningful information.
- *Transformation Algorithm* - Mapping EEG information to control parameters within a musical engine.
- *Visual Stimuli* – This elicits the EEG data and provides real-time feedback to the user.
- *Musical Engine* – This is the musical interpretation of the EEG data, which is presented as a score to a musician.

Figure 1. The components of the Brain-Computer Music Interfacing system. This diagram illustrates how EEG data is mapped to a separate computer screen for

displaying the score, and a stimuli display with visual feedback.

3. SSVEP

Aside from the use of alpha rhythms BCMI have utilised other techniques of harnessing brainwave information to control music. These include stimulating P300 ERPs [15], auditory imagery [16] and different methods of data classification [6] [17]. A recent survey of BCI techniques by the commercial company G.tec has validated SSVEP as currently the most accurate and responsive method for BCI user control [18] confirming it to be ideal for real-time control over precise values.

The issue of interpreting meaning in EEG signals for control has long been a focus within BCMI research [7]. The SSVEP technique allows for such precise control that meaning can be injected into the design of a system, allowing for simplicity or complexity dependant on the requirements of the application.

3.1 Eliciting Potentials

ERPs are spikes of brainwave activity produced by perception to stimuli presented to a subject. They are time locked to the event of the stimuli and as such the ERP response to a single event is problematic to detect in EEG on a single trial basis, as it becomes lost in the general noise of on-going electrical brain activity. However, if a user is subjected to repeated visual stimulation at short intervals (at rates approximately between 5Hz – 30Hz), then before the signal has had a chance to return back to its unexcited state the rapid introduction of the next flashing onset elicits another response. Further successive flashes induce what is known as the steady-state response, a continuously evoked amplification of the brainwave [19]. This negates a need for performing numerous delayed trials as the repeated visuals are consistently providing the stimuli required for a constant potential, translated as a consistent increased amplitude level in the associated EEG frequency.

This technique, SSEVP, was adopted in a BCMI system designed for testing with a patient with locked in syndrome [8] as a tool for providing recreational music making. Here four flashing icons (between 6 – 15Hz) were presented on a computer screen, their flashing frequencies relative to the frequencies of corresponding brainwaves. A user selects an icon by gazing at one and as a result of this action the amplitude of the corresponding brainwave frequency, measured in the visual cortex, increases. Here the EEG is analysed continuously, looking for amplitude changes within the four frequencies. The icons represent four choices, always available to the user at the same time. These icons are in turn mapped to commands within a musical engine providing explicit meaning to each icon. The instantaneous speed of the EEG response to the stimuli offers real-time control of a BCMI, which requires no user or system training beyond the task of visual focusing. When the analysis software detects an increase in an SSVEP channel a control signal is feedback to the visual interface providing feedback to the user.

3.2 Amplitude Control

As well as the selection of commands a second dimension of control was gathered through the level of visual focusing. This elicited a relative linear response within the amplitude of the corresponding brain wave. This allows users to employ proportional control methods akin to intrinsically analogue tasks such as pushing a fader or turning a dial. This differs from previous selective, more digital tasks in BCMI, such as a switch or a toggle function. In previous implementations we utilised this control to trigger a series of defined notes within a scale [8] and for more complex mapping techniques [9].

Our SSVEP approach requires the presence of 3 electrodes (using the 10-20 placement system), training comprising verbal instructions and a calibration time of approximately 2 minutes per user.

Figure 2. The visual stimuli screen as presented to a user. Note the differences in spatial frequency of checker patterns and the feedback ring around the left hand icon which increases in size and colour intensity relative to the power of the corresponding EEG frequency.

4. PRACTICALITIES IN BCMI DESIGN

We are keen to take BCMI research out of the laboratory and into more practical settings. Consequently, for the system presented here we were keen to use portable laptop computers and EEG systems with wireless electrodes. Currently high-end medical EEG systems are expensive, delicate and inefficient to transport and setup. In recent years headsets aimed at the prosumer market from companies such as NeuroSky and Emotiv offer affordable EEG platforms, but at the expense of accuracy. We have therefore bypassed more advanced amplitude control, discussed in Section 3, in favour of a simpler method using single threshold values where a value rising over a set threshold acts as a switch. In the system presented here we have adopted the Emotiv headset with bespoke signal processing software to drive the JMSL MaxScore notation platform.

4.1 Visual Interface Considerations

To elicit SSVEP a stable visual interface is required that updates precisely, without frame drops or variations in frequency. A good quality graphics card can, by today's standard, provide the processing required for this, but for laptop computers (high-end gaming laptops aside) this can be a struggle.

There are two options available for SSVEP stimuli design. Single graphics stimuli have icons that alternate between a pair of colours (black and white and red and green being the two pairs most suitable). These flicker between two alternations per frequency cycle. Pattern reversal icons with a checkerboard pattern only require one alternation per cycle, whereby the pattern is reversed [20]. Icons that use pattern reversal require particular attention to the spatial frequency of the patterns used, and this should be optimised for best results with each frequency band. The icons in Figure 2 display different spatial frequencies for different frequency bands; a larger spatial frequency for faster flashing rates and vice versa [21].

Figure 3. Diagram displaying the frame combination to elicit a 12Hz SSVEP response with single graphics stimuli and pattern reversal.

Calculating the rate of flashes in both cases requires dividing icon onset instances into integers of the screen's refresh rate [22]. For example a 12Hz single graphics stimuli with a 60Hz screen refresh rate would complete one full cycle (two alternations) every 5 frames, whereas pattern reversal stimuli would require only one alternation over the same period to elicit SSVEP (see Figure 3). As shown in Figure 3 there are 50% fewer alternations required per cycle using the pattern reversal stimuli. This reduction diminishes the graphics processing required providing a more stable technique for the laptops we used.

5. MIND TRIO

Musikalisches Würfelspiel, a music style of German origin, can be considered as an early form of generative music that was popularised in 18th Century Europe. Composing employed a system that used dice to randomly select small sections of pre-composed music resulting in a piece that would differ upon every iteration. Mozart's K6.516f, for instrumental trio, is widely thought to be derived from this method, and in another work attributed to him the score's accompanying commentary begins its instructions with the line 'To compose, without the least

knowledge of music, so many [scores] as one pleases...'[23]. We have adapted this idea and twisted our interpretation to allow for composing with knowledge of what one is doing to the music.

The BCMI user plays the part of composer in Mind Trio, arranging the structure of the musical score. The purpose of our game is to choose from a selection of musical phrases, which in turn builds the score of the piece. From user selection via icon gazing a score is arranged then visually updated on a separate computer screen at regular intervals in time.

Figure 4 illustrates the concept of the compositional game. With the current musical phrase set to 56 the four icon choices represent the next four possibilities in the pathway matrix. By selecting the left hand icon Phrase 73 is selected as the next element in the composition, and the game repeats. With Phrase 73 as the current Phrase the icons will then switch to represent choices of phrase 59, 42, 54, 16, and so on.

Figure 4. The compositional strategy for playing Mind Trio shows how to build a continuous score from Phrase 56 to Phrase 73. Note that the diagram shows only an excerpt of the pathway matrix.

5.1 System Design

Mind Trio is a musical piece designed for BCMI user and solo pianist. The BCMI user, wearing a wireless headset, sends EEG data to a primary laptop. Signal processing software analyses the incoming EEG data stream assessing relevant SSVEP activity using Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis of frequency bandwidths held

in the stimuli. EEG data is converted into a control signal sent to the visual interface displayed to the performer via the primary laptop. The control signal is sent to a secondary laptop where the transformation algorithm handles the mappings of the control data to direct the notation, which is presented for the pianist via the laptop's display screen (see Figure 1).

5.2 Real-Time Notation

For Mind Trio an array of 96 pre-composed musical phrases are allocated sequentially into four pathways in the pathway matrix. During playback the BCMI user selects a pathway using the associated icon and the score presented on screen updates to shift to this pathway at the next display onset time. Here, the musician does not know what is on the next page until it is automatically (digitally) turned.

In order for a system with a continuously updating score to function successfully a musician must be able to read musical segments of at least a few seconds at once. The display is divided into two lines of two bars, and with a mean tempo of 60bpm and a 4/4 time signature the page display onset time equates to approximately 8 seconds; this is adequate for a musician of a professional standard to work with.

As the mapping of icons to pathways is relatively straightforward there is little computation time required, allowing the BCMI user a large window during each page display during which to make their selection. The piece begins in pathway 1 and during any window if no selection is made then the current pathway remains. If a pathway reaches the end of its 24 phrases it simply continues in a circular style from the beginning.

It is worth noting that in more complex mapping systems the selection window may need to be shortened to account for algorithmic processing as well as account for multiple selections over a range of parameters. Also a more complex score is likely to coincide with less accuracy from a musician. This is also owing to the fact that there is no possibility to rehearse an exact piece, as each composition will differ from the last.

Figure 5. A prototype of the notation system in action. The user gazes at the icons on the left hand screen, which, seconds later, updates the score on the right hand screen.

6. MULTIPLE BCMI USERS

To further our work integrating BCMI users and musicians we aim to build a system whereby multiple users can control multiple scores within the same piece. We have successfully trialled a version of our system with multiple users controlling musical parameters of pre-composed electronic music. Figure 6 below shows two subjects affecting elements of the same electronic composition as a way of composing together, expanding the concept of neurofeedback. Here, feedback not only exists in single loops between subjects and computers as the paths of neurofeedback loops change as they influence and combine with other subjects at different times. The musical outcomes of this setting pose an exciting playground for experimentation and creative music making. Our aim is to integrate this collaborative approach into our notation system whereby four BCMI users control micro, meso, and macro features of a score for a string quartet. We hope to have this system ready for performance by early 2014.

Figure 6. Two subjects enjoy composing music in a multi-user scenario. Each subject is controlling parameters of a group of instruments via the mappings of each icon. User 1 controls percussive sounds and user 2 controls melodic phrases.

7. DISCUSSION

Our research successfully demonstrates the suitability of the SSVEP technique for eliciting control over musical notation in the continuous fashion required for acoustic music performance. Furthermore our system highlights that SSVEP control is achievable using portable and affordable equipment that is subsequently more practical for use in real-world environments; it requires minimal calibration, apparatus and setup time. By harnessing brain signals in this manner the neurofeedback loop that is created between the BCMI user and the resulting music is extended to include a musician. This is a significant step in the design of new BCMI tools. We have demonstrated how SSVEP interfaces can be designed for consumer level laptop computers, widening access to the technologies required for BCMI, as well as for users with limited motor capabilities.

In practice the current iteration of the system is straightforward to use. The nature of MindTrio requires a user to be familiar with the musical pathways for the results of decisions to be pre-determined. For future iterations that affect more complex elements of notation the user inter-

face requires adaption to translate the decisions simply alongside or within the stimulating icons.

There are still key issues that plague the stability of composing with brainwaves, which affect the usability and accuracy of measuring brain signals with this technology, more significantly than high-end medical systems and outside of the controlled environment of the laboratory.

Non-invasive EEG measures brain waves through electrodes placed on the scalp. Yet amplifying very low level electrical signals (as low as only a few microvolts) that are filtered through the skull, membrane, hair and skin results in significant noise levels alongside interference from other electrical sources and the continual electrical activity of non-related EEG. Although SSVEP provides relative high accuracy extracting meaning within EEG signals still requires complex signal analysis tools and is also largely reflected in the quality of the hardware components.

The system we have constructed here offers a compromising solution to these difficulties. The interface and signal processing software is robust and performs well in response to the real-time EEG data, but the Emotiv hardware offers a less stable interface for measuring accurate brain signals than more expensive and less portable platforms. This accuracy is noticeable in practice but is tolerable for MindTunes as real-time feedback is certainly present providing the response and feeling of control to a user. We predict that for embedding more complex control systems beyond straightforward selection then issues may arise.

Mind Trio presents a simple proof-of-concept system that paves the way for more advanced compositional techniques and mapping strategies using digital notation presented to musicians. By injecting more complex meaning within the design of such systems, higher levels of musical complexity can be offered and subsequently controlled. For example, a well as directing structural pathways, more expressive parameters and nuances such as harmonic structure, playing technique or dynamic and rhythmic changes, can be chosen via the BCMI. This expansion, coupled with multiple users poses an exciting platform for creative composition and BCMI design.

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